

ASSESSMENT OF LAND DEGRADATION THROUGH THE TRENDS.EARTH PLATFORM

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Abstract . This article describes the capabilities of the Trends.Earth platform in solving the problem of land degradation elimination, accurate and reliable assessment of land degradation. Also mapping according to SDG 15.3.1 indicator, information on the benefits of this tool for identifying, monitoring and decision-making of degraded areas using satellite images and data.

Key words: GIS technologies , soil degradation , Trends.Earth platform , LD, SDG, NDVI, remote sensing , database, modeling.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yer degradatsiyasini aniq va ishonchli baholash yer degradatsiyasini bartaraf etish muammosini hal qilishda Trends.Earth–platformasining imkoniyatlari bayon qilingan. Shuningdek, SDG 15.3.1 indikatori bo'yicha xaritalash, sun'iy yo'ldosh tasvirlari va ma'lumotlaridan foydalang holda degradatsiyaga uchragan maydonlarni aniqlash, monitiring qilish va qaror qabul qilishda ushbu vositaning afzalliklari bo'yicha ma'lumotlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: GAT texnologiyalari, tuproq degradatsiyasi, Trends.Earth platformasi, LD, SDG, NDVI, masofaviy zondlash, ma'lumotlar bazasi, modellashtirish.

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны возможности платформы Trends.Earth в решении проблемы устранения деградации земель, точной и достоверной оценки деградации земель. Также выделена информация о преимуществах этого инструмента для выявления, мониторинга и принятия решений деградированных территорий с использованием спутниковых изображений и данных для картографирования, индикатора SDG 15.3.1.

Ключевые слова: технологии GAT, деградация почв, платформа Trends.Earth, LD, SDG, NDVI, дистанционное зондирование, база данных, моделирование.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations , 33% of the world's soils have been degraded, and the degradation may continue to reach 90% by 2050.

Today, the quality and composition of the irrigated soils of our republic is changing every year, therefore, it is necessary to determine the degradation processes that affect the fertility of the soil, to develop scientific solutions aimed at preventing such negative processes, and to increase and protect soil fertility. measures are being implemented. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5742 "On measures for effective use of land and water resources in agriculture" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 10, 2022 "Effective fight against land degradation" In the Resolution No. PQ-277 on measures to create a system of land degradation, desertification and drought in our country, prevention of land degradation processes and combating them, elimination of negative consequences, degradation of land restoration , wide introduction of advanced technologies in this direction [1], monitoring of agricultural land, use of geodetic data and cartographic materials, aerospace, topographic-geodetic, cartographic, soil, geobotanical and other carrying out research, carrying out cartographic work using remote sensing data, organizing work aimed at the widespread use of modern information and communication technologies [2]. That's why monitoring of arable land in the republic, in

particular, improvement through the use of innovative technologies, their effective use is of great importance.

To date, the development of GIS technologies has reached a high stage: extensive work is being carried out on the implementation of special GIS technologies, which are aimed at using them in production, from the stage of mastering the capabilities of software and hardware tools through the creation of various digital maps and databases [3]. One of the most important tasks is the creation of specially oriented maps based on existing and newly acquired data.

The Trends.Earth platform is a modern platform that allows you to monitor the changes on the ground using the above-mentioned issues, that is, ground observations. Using the Trends.Earth platform, we can obtain general understanding of indicators that determine the productivity of irrigated soils to significantly minimize or eliminate land degradation[4].

Indicator 15.3.1 of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) uses data from 3 sub-indicators to assess degraded areas. These include:

1. Land productivity is the biological productivity of the land, which provides all the food, fiber and fuel

sources for human life .

2. Soil cover - consisting of unique natural forms of the earth, these are soil-forming rocks, depending on the intensity of the influence of biochemical and biological processes on them, it is the biologically active upper crust of the Earth, which is different in terms of fertility and fertility in different regions.

3. Soil organic carbon Specific carbon-related indicators used to assess soil health include CO₂ release, humus content, and microbial metabolic activity.

Land degradation neutrality (LDN) is a state in which the quantity and quality of land resources remain stable or increase over a defined temporal and spatial scale [5]. Achieving this requires the adoption of sustainable land management (SLM) practices to increase the sustainable provision of ecosystem goods and services required by human populations. It also requires the development of systematic, robust and validated methods for monitoring research at the project, sub-national and national levels.

In the works of I. Cherif, E. Kolintziki, among the existing methods of calculating land productivity, factors using NDVI trends were used. Although this method does not consider the influence of climate on LD, it is recommended to be used in irrigated agricultural areas to avoid water effects[6]. Thus, in this study, land degradation can be seen regardless of its causes - human or climate .

On the Trends.Earth platform, land productivity is divided into several classes (decreasing, early signs of decline, stable growth), and according to the SDG 15.3.1 indicator, three classes (Degraded, Stable, Improved) are considered [7].

This platform allows users to monitor the impact of sustainable land degradation management by assessing key indicators of land change for mapping and creating various graphs. The platform uses the results of monitoring progress on land degradation neutrality (SDG 15.3.1), land use (SDG 11.3.1), modeling carbon emissions from deforestation and modeling associated potential carbon sequestration following restoration activities [8].

Trends.Earth facilitates monitoring and reporting on indicators 15.3.1 (area of degraded land) and 11.3.1 (ratio of land use to population growth) of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) [9].

The Trends.Earth platform developed by Conservation International is a convenient and widely used platform for monitoring indicators for several SDGs. It takes data from a number of global data sets, aggregates data available at the national level and uses a cloud-based approach based on Google Earth Engine to calculate subsequent indicators, with the final indicator determined according to local ledgers. . The use of this platform is recommended by the UNCCD for monitoring and reporting of land degradation by national agencies. The Trends.Earth platform calculates the indicators separately for the country and region boundaries or the user-defined area and then combines them into the SDG 15.3.1 indicator. The results are generated as Excel files with ready indicators and raster maps in UNCCD compliant format [10].

Conclusion

It can be used indicators created by Trends.Earth (<http://trends.earth>), a free and open source system for calculating land degradation indicators. Trends.Earth is a valuable tool for LD monitoring. It is also easy to customize for use with specific data sets and specific areas of interest. Land degradation using the SDG 15.3.1 indicator we can obtain general data on land degradation using the Trends.Earth platform. It is no exaggeration to say that the use of this platform is considered effective for measures aimed at monitoring and preventing soil degradation processes observed in our republic

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